

MICROSTRUCTURAL EVOLUTION AND ELECTROMAGNETIC PROPERTIES OF IRON NANOFIBERS SYNTHESIZED BY THE ELECTROSPINNING PROCESS

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SUMMARY

For development of efficient electromagnetic (EM) wave absorbing materials in giga-hertz band, Fe nanofibers with high aspect ratio have been synthesized by the multi-nozzle electrospinning process coupled with heat treatments of calcinations and reduction. The effects of applied voltage and feed rate on the morphology of electrospun PVP/Fe salt nanofibers were examined. The average diameter and standard deviation of electrospun nanofibers tended to decrease with increasing applied voltage and with decreasing feed rate, respectively. By H₂ reduction process following calcination process, as-spun PVP/Fe salt was transformed step-by-step into Fe₂O₃ phase, Fe₃O₄ phase, and Fe phase. To evaluate EM characteristics of synthesized Fe nanofibers, the homogeneous composites containing Fe nanofibers of 10 and 30 wt% were successfully fabricated by shear mixing method. Fe nanofibers improved EM characteristics of composites compared with conventional metallic spheres. Based on the results, it was concluded that Fe nanofibers were effective fillers for development of efficient EM wave absorbing materials in high frequency band.

Keywords: electrospinning, Fe nanofibers, composite, electromagnetic absorbing, uniform dispersion

INTRODUCTION

Giga-hertz (GHz) electromagnetic (EM) waves are increasingly being applied in industry because of saturation at lower frequency band as a result of huge demand [1-2]. In application of high frequency EM waves, the problems such as electromagnetic interference (EMI), noise generation, harmful EM waves to human are big issue in electronics, telecommunication and military communication. Therefore, the technology of high frequency EM shielding, especially EM absorbing, has received increasing attention in recent years. In a viewpoint of materials, major researches have been conducted on the development of efficient fillers and EM absorbing materials with thin, light, broad absorbing bandwidths (BWs) as well as high frequency. Typically, EM

wave absorbing characteristics depend on permittivity, permeability, and thickness of materials and frequency of application.

Commercially, EM absorbing materials are made of composites, which blend the insulating polymer with fillers such as conductive carbon nanoparticles, ferrites, and metallic magnetic microparticles. Absorbing materials employing conductive carbon nanoparticles such as CB, CNF, and CNT have high permittivity and light weight, but have disadvantages of thick matching thicknesses and narrow BWs [2,3]. Magnetic absorbing materials using micron-sized fillers, however, suffer from heavy weight and poor EM characteristics in GHz frequency ranges due to Snoek's limit [4,5] in case of ferrites and skin depth effect in case of magnetic metals [6]. Therefore, high permeability as well as high permittivity of fillers at GHz ranges is indispensable for development of thin, light, and high-performance absorbers with broad BWs. Magnetic metallic nanofibers with high aspect ratio can display high permittivity and permeability values at GHz frequency ranges because of their forming ability of bigger electric and magnetic dipoles and conductive networks in addition to effect of nano-dimension to eliminate eddy current loss [7,8]. High aspect ratio nanofibers have been fabricated by employing the drawing [9], template synthesis [10], phase separation [11], self assembly [12], and electrospinning process [13,14]. Electrospinning process as a simple, convenient, and cost-effective sol-gel method makes it possible to fabricate fibers with long length, uniformity in diameter ranging from tens of nanometers to several micrometers, and diversification in compositions [15,16].

In this study, Fe nanofibers with high aspect ratio were successfully synthesized by multi-nozzle electrospinning process and heat treatments. The mechanism of their microstructural evolution in synthetic processes was analyzed with SEM/EDS and XRD. The composites with Fe nanofibers of 10 and 30 wt% were fabricated by mechanical mixing process, and their microstructures were observed with SEM to confirm the homogeneous dispersion of nanofibers in composites. Besides, to estimate the EM characteristics of composites, their permittivities and permeabilities were measured with network analyzer.

EXPERIMENTALS

Materials

Polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP, $M_w=1,300,000$) and anhydrous ethanol (99.5+ %) were supplied by Sigma-Aldrich, Inc. Iron (III) nitrate nonahydrate (Fe nitrate, $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 99.9%) was purchased from High Purity Chemicals and used as the precursor for Fe. 29.03 g of Fe nitrate was dissolved in 9 ml of distilled water and stirred until completely dissolved. The PVP solution was prepared using 1.5 g PVP with 36 g anhydrous ethanol as the solvent under constant and vigorous stirring for 30 min. After dissolution of all compounds, the Fe nitrate solution was mixed with the PVP solution under continuous stirring at room temperature for 30 min. Then, a dark red sol solution with a PVP:Fe volume ratio of 70:30 was obtained as the final electrospinning solution.

Electrospinning process

The prepared solution was loaded into a plastic syringe that was connected to 50 series nozzles with needle-type (inner diameter of 0.15 mm). A copper pin connected to a high-voltage generator was placed in the solution. Voltages of 20, 24, 28, and 32 kV, respectively, were applied between the nozzle and the collector. The nozzle tip-to-collector distance was 10 cm. Also, the solution was supplied at various feed rates of 2, 3, 4, and 5 ml/hr, respectively, using a syringe pump (KD scientific KDS-100). Both temperatures of solution and atmosphere were controlled as a value of 40°C. A rotating drum with diameter of 20 cm and length of 30 cm was used as a collector with a rotating speed of 300 rpm. The process was conducted vertically. Figure 1 displays the schematic diagram of electrospinning process used in this study.

Figure 1. Schematic illustration of multi-nozzle electrospinning process.

Heat treatment of nanofibers

To determine the optimal process condition of electrospinning, as-spun nanofibers were observed with scanning electron microscope (SEM). Based on the image analyses of nanofibers in each process condition, the averages and the standard deviations of their diameters were characterized. To fabricate Fe nanofibers, first PVP/Fe salt nanofibers were calcined at air condition of 600°C for 1 hr, and then reduced at condition of high-purity hydrogen atmosphere (flow rate of 5 ml/sec) of 400°C for 30 min. The as-spun, calcined, and hydrogen-reduced nanofibers, respectively, were characterized by SEM and x-ray diffractometer (XRD).

Fabrication of composites & measurement of EM characteristics

To fabricate composite with uniform dispersion, the heat treated Fe nanofibers were grinded to relatively short fibres. Composites containing grinded Fe nanofibers were fabricated with the different concentrations. The mixtures of epoxy resin and Fe nanofibers with net concentrations of 10 and 30 wt% were stirred by homomixer for 20 min. After those mixtures were degassed for 20 min, they were cured at 120°C, 2 hr. The microstructures of composites were observed with SEM.

The composites were cut into cylindrical toroids (inner and outer diameters of 3.0 and 7.0 mm, respectively). Their complex permittivities and permeabilities were measured in the 2~18 GHz frequency range using a network analyzer.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Electrospun nanofibers

The process parameter to influence the morphology of electrospun nanofibers includes applied voltage, feed rate and temperature of solution, atmosphere, diameter of nozzle, distance between the nozzle tip and collector, type of collector, and so on. In this study, applied voltage and feed rate were changed as main process parameters and the other parameters were fixed. SEM images of electrospun PVP/Fe salt nanofibers synthesized at different conditions of feed rate and applied voltage are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. SEM morphologies of electrospun PVP/Fe salt nanofibers synthesized at different conditions of feed rate and applied voltage: feed rate of 2 ml/hr at applied voltage of (a) 20, (b) 24, (c) 28, and (d) 32 kV, respectively, feed rate of 3 ml/hr at applied voltage of (e) 20, (f) 24, (g) 28, and (h) 32 kV, respectively, feed rate of 4 ml/hr at applied voltage of (i) 20, (j) 24, (k) 28, and (l) 32 kV, respectively, and feed rate of 5 ml/hr at applied voltage of (m) 20, (n) 24, (o) 28, and (p) 32 kV, respectively.

In same feed rate of solution, both of diameters and deviation of nanofibers decrease as the applied voltage increases. High electric field and columbic repulsive force in solution jet induced by higher applied voltage causes to accelerate and to stretch the solution jet thoroughly. Therefore, this results in smaller average diameter and deviation of nanofibers [17]. Average diameters of electrospun PVP/Fe salt nanofibers and the standard deviations of them as function of applied voltage and feed rate are summarized in Figure 3. As shown in graphs, trend of decreases in average diameters and standard deviations with applied voltage can be found quantitatively. Also it is confirmed that increases in average diameters and standard deviations with feed rate. In this study, 50 series nozzles were used to fabricate a large amount of nanofibers with uniform dimension. Up to feed rate of 4 ml/hr, the relatively uniform nanofibers were fabricated in each applied voltage. In feed rate of 5 ml/hr, the standard deviation of them increased drastically and lots of beads were observed. If there is a corresponding increase of electric fields and volumes of solution in every nozzle tips when feed rate is increased, the liquid jets are stable and stretched and the average diameter of nanofibers increases. As matter of course, it needs an adequate flight time to dry the residual solvent in solution jets. Based on the results of electrospinning process, the applied voltage of 32 kV and the feed rate of 4 ml/hr were chosen as optimal process condition since they could be productive and fabricated the nanofibers with relatively small diameter and deviation.

Figure 3. Average diameters of electrospun PVP/Fe salt nanofibers and the standard deviations of fiber diameters as function of applied voltage and feed rate.

Microstructural evolution

Two stages heat treatment of calcination and H₂ reduction was conducted to produce metallic nanofibers from as-spun PVP/Fe salt nanofibers. Their conditions were determined based on the results of TG-DTA curves, respectively. PVP and the organic groups of Fe nitrate were almost completely removed above 500°C. In this study, as-spun nanofibers were calcined at 600°C for 1 hr in air to fabricate Fe oxide nanofibers. Figure 4(a) and (b) show SEM images of as-spun nanofibers fabricated in the condition of the applied voltage of 32 kV and the feed rate of 4 ml/hr and as-calcined nanofibers, respectively. The average diameter of as-spun nanofibers was approximately 330 nm. After calcinations, the average diameter of nanofibers decreased to approximately 260

nm because of decomposition of PVP. According to TG-DTA result in H₂ atmosphere, the weight loss of Fe oxide nanofibers proceeded up to 400°C. Therefore, as-calcined oxide nanofibers were treated at 400°C for 30 min in high purity H₂ atmosphere for reduction. Figure 4(c) shows SEM image of as-reduced nanofibers. The average diameter of them decreased to approximately 200 nm due to phase transformation from Fe oxide to metallic Fe.

Figure 4. SEM micrographs of nanofibers at different stages of heat treatments: (a) as-spun, (b) as-calcined and (c) as-reduced, respectively.

Figure 5 shows the XRD results of as-calcined nanofibers and as-reduced nanofibers to analyze the phase transformation behavior. The amorphous phase of PVP/Fe salt nanofibers was transformed into Fe₂O₃ phase during calcination process since Fe in salt nanofibers combined with oxygen in air. The Fe₂O₃ was identified with analysis of diffraction peaks in Figure 5(a). In reduction stage, Fe₂O₃ phase was transformed into Fe phase by the following reduction mechanism [19].

The H₂ reduction mechanism of Fe₂O₃ is divided by two steps as equations (1) and (2). In first step, Fe₃O₄ phase was synthesized by reaction of Fe₂O₃ phase and H₂ gas. And

then Fe_3O_4 phase was transformed into pure Fe phase by additional reaction of reduction. The diffraction peaks in Figure 5(b) were identified as Fe_3O_4 and BCC Fe phases, respectively. The existence of Fe_3O_4 phase can be explained with two causes. One is an incomplete reduction of Fe_3O_4 phase. The other is a re-oxidation of reduced nanofibers. The nano-sized Fe particles with an amount of surface are easily oxidized when they are exposed in at room temperature in air. If necessary, the surface of Fe nanofibers can be coated with polymer or ceramic to prevent re-oxidation of them.

Figure 5. XRD patterns of nanofibers at different stage of heat treatments: (a) as-calcined at 600°C for 1 hr and (b) as-reduced at 400°C for 30 min, respectively.

Composites & EM properties

To evaluate EM characteristics of synthesized Fe nanofibers, epoxy matrix composites containing them were fabricated. In measurement of the precise EM properties of composites, it is very important to disperse homogeneously them in polymer matrix. However, the morphology of as-reduced Fe nanofibers was a web of continuous fibers which had lots of fused nodes. This agglomerate of Fe nanofibers causes to precipitations due to high specific gravity in polymer media with low specific gravity. To prepare uniform composites, firstly the webs of Fe nanofibers were grinded to relatively short fibres, and then the mixtures of epoxy resin and grinded nanofibers were homogenized by mechanical stirrer with strong shear force. Figure 6 shows the SEM images of the composites containing Fe nanofibers of 10 and 30 wt% (CF10 and CF30), respectively. Fe nanofibers were uniformly distributed in epoxy matrix and any aggregates or precipitated parts of them were not observed through the composites. This result indicates that sound composites to evaluate EM characteristics of synthesized Fe nanofibers were fabricated by the methods as stated above.

Figure 6. Low and High magnification SEM micrographs of epoxy composites containing Fe nanofibers: (a), (b) 10 wt% and (c), (d) 30 wt%, respectively.

The complex permittivities and permeabilities of CF10 and CF30 were measured in the 2~18 GHz frequency range using a network analyzer. Their complex permittivities are shown in Figure 7(a). Both real and imaginary parts of permittivity increased with the content of Fe nanofibers. Figure 7(b) shows the complex permeabilities of CF10 and CF30. The permeabilities also increased with the content of Fe nanofibers, but the change of them was relatively low compared with the permittivities.

Figure 7. EM properties of Fe nanofiber/epoxy composites: (a) permittivity and (b) permeability, respectively.

The real and imaginary parts of permittivity of CF30 were distributed in the range of $17 < \epsilon_r' < 25$ and $4.7 < \epsilon_r'' < 5.6$, respectively. In previous study, the values of epoxy composite containing 50 wt% Fe nanopowders were measured in the range of $8 < \epsilon_r' < 9$ and $0.5 < \epsilon_r'' < 0.7$, respectively. The formations of bigger electric and magnetic dipoles as well as conductive networks are easy as an aspect ratio of fillers increases. Pullar et al. reported that effective EM properties could be enhanced in fine fibrous form although intrinsic properties are not changed since the concentration of percolation threshold becomes lower and the influence of fiber alignment becomes higher when a field is applied to the same direction as fiber alignment [20]. In this study, Fe nanofibers of high aspect ratio improved the permittivities and permeabilities compared with simple metallic spheres or particles of low aspect ratio. These results indicate that Fe nanofibers are effective fillers for development of efficient EM wave absorbing materials in high frequency band.

CONCLUSIONS

In order to increase the EM wave absorbing properties in GHz frequency region, high aspect ratio Fe nanofibers have been successfully synthesized by the multi-nozzle electrospinning process coupled with heat treatments of calcinations and reduction. The Fe nanofiber/epoxy composites were fabricated with contents of 10 and 30 wt% and their permittivities and permeabilities were evaluated. Based the results, following conclusions were drawn.

1. The average diameter and standard deviation of electrospun nanofibers tended to decrease with increasing applied voltage and decreasing feed rate.
2. As-spun PVP/Fe salt was transformed step-by-step into Fe_2O_3 phase, Fe_3O_4 phase, and Fe phase by calcinations and H_2 reduction.
3. Fe nanofibers of high aspect ratio improved the permittivities and permeabilities compared with simple metallic spheres or particles with low aspect ratio.

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